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“MIDDLE ENGLISH: A PERIOD OF GREAT CHANGE”

English language is never perfectly stable. It keeps changing, evolving, and adapting to the needs of the users influenced by social, political, and economic subsistence of the language, society, and culture. The truth why language changes can be largely accounted to the combination of internal change and external influences. Ghosal (2016) in an online forum examined the history of English and discussed that the external history of English language is comprised of the events like the early migration of the Celts, Roman rule over Celts, the invasion and settlement of certain Germanic tribes in an island, the arrival of St. Augustine's and the Christianization of English race, repeated invasions of the Scandinavians, the Norman conquest, the Renaissance, the industrialization, and the spread of the English race through migration and/or colonization. He furthered that the concomitant internal history would subsume the changes in sound, changes of some alphabetical shape, the structural change (from synthetic to analytic), and huge borrowing of foreign words against the loss of early English words.

Drawing from the above insights, the Middle English period (1150 – 1500) is a period rich with many dramatic developments on the areas of **literature** and **linguistics** of the English language which signaled a radical and fundamental change of the English language to take on an identity of its own after the Norman conquest until the late 15th century. The ME literary and linguistic achievements were often the result of invasions or migrations and were also said to be the result of the long accommodation between the Germanic language of the Anglo-Saxons (Old English) and the Latin-based language of the Norman French under William the Conqueror in 1066 at the Battle of Hastings where he challenged King Harold of England in the struggle for the English throne. **Hurley (2014)** on the History of English espoused that the Norman invasion had a profound effect on England's institutions and its language. The Normans looked upon the Anglo-Saxons as social inferiors; eventually, French became the language of the court and English was the language of people. England experienced diglossic situation, with French as the high prestige and English as the low prestige variety. Thus, England and France began to develop rivalry that culminated in the hundred years war.

Fennel (2001) in her book, *A History of English: A Sociolinguistic Approach*, provided a comprehensive overview of the history of English where she revealed that when rivalry between France and England developed, the interests of the two could no longer be the same, so it ultimately resulted in the re-establishment of English. “The nobility's use of French was a matter of culture and fashion, that is, a sociological choice rather than an economic and political necessity; the nobility chose to maintain French as the language of society, administration, and commerce until the use of English began to spread even amongst the nobility”, she quipped. This means that English was already common at all levels of society, in governmental, administrative, legal, and literary contexts, texts, and manuscripts, completely eradicating French in 1489 as the language of Parliament.

This major paradigm shift in history has paved the way to approach the flowering changes of Middle English linguistics and literature than those that have taken place at any time before or since.

On Linguistics

The Middle English period was marked by significant changes in the English language particularly on two linguistic developments, to wit: in grammar and in vocabulary. Linguists after comparing the English written texts revealed the following differences between Old English and Middle English; that is, the former (OE) might be called a synthetic language which uses inflectional morphemes to express the synthetical relationships whereas the latter (ME) might be called an analytical language which uses function words to constitute syntactical relationships.

Baugh and Cable (2002) exhaustively examined some significant linguistic features of Middle English and distinguished the following notable grammar and vocabulary changes such as decay of inflectional endings, loss of strong verbs, ambiguous syntax, consequent simplification of English grammar, and loss of grammatical gender. They described the changes in English grammar as a general reduction of inflections. They also added that endings of the noun and adjective marking distinctions of number and case and often of gender were so altered in pronunciation as to lose their distinctive form and hence their usefulness. On the loss of strong verbs, Baugh and Cable noticed that more than a hundred of the Old English strong verbs were lost at the beginning of the ME period.

In ME grammar, Durkin (2013) posed that English came to rely less on inflectional endings and more on word order convey grammatical information. He also shared the same findings with Baugh and Cable that ME grammatical gender was lost early in ME period. He identified the reduction of the range of inflections, particularly in the noun (partly as a result of reduction of vowels in unstressed final syllables), as was the number of distinct paradigms: in most early Middle English texts, most nouns have distinctive forms only for singular vs. plural, genitive, occasional traces of the old dative in forms with final -e occurring after a preposition.

Gastle (2009) also ascertained that the English language changed dramatically that it gradually lost its inflections (word suffixes that controlled meaning) and relied more on word order for meaning after the Norman Conquest. That is why, according to him, French words became a more significant part of English vocabulary, and often the French form of a word became the more socially prestigious for of the word. An example was given by Gastle, showing how the following words below meant the same thing but have now come to carry much different connotations.

“stench” (OE *stenc/stincan*) and “aroma” (OF *aromat*): the French have an *aroma* and the English *stink*

“ask” (OE *ascian*) and “demand” (OF *desmande*): the English, as subordinates, *ask* and the French, as superiors, *demand*.

“cow” (OE *cu*) and “beef” (OF *boef*).

At the level of syntax where the study of grammaticalization became considerably interesting during ME period, the most explicit discussion of the matter is due to Kroch and Taylor (2000) in their study on Verb-Object Order in Early Middle English. Based on their findings of their first extensive quantitative analysis of Middle English syntax, they concluded that all early Middle English texts exhibit a small remnant of INFL (inflectional) -final word order, suggesting continuity with late Old English. Second, their study showed leftward scrambling of both pronouns and full nouns phrases across the untensed verb in VO clauses with auxiliary verbs. They further emphasized that they have assumed that variation in underlying word order is possible within texts and, based on that assumption, have been able to account for both categorical and frequentistic aspects of early ME word order patterning.

Another study conducted by Kleinman (2009) has given the writer valuable insights on the developments of ME grammar. Kleinman noted that plurals of nouns generally end in -s or -es; however, some nouns end in -n or -en.

Also, he cited that the possessive forms end in –s or –es that possessives are distinguished from plurals by context and not by apostrophe. ME infinitive form (e.g. ‘to go’, ‘to sleep’, ‘to sing’), according to his findings, ends in –n or –en: e.g. goon, slepen, singen which can also indicate a plural form of the verb.

There are also profound changes in the vocabulary when colonists from England arrived and settled in the place. Baugh and Cable (2002) described these changes as the *Breadth of the French Influence* in which the French language altered the English vocabulary in the middle Ages. They enumerated a miscellaneous list of words- nouns, adjectives, and verbs – to realize how universal was the French contribution. The following list made up of words that were already in English by 1300: *action, adventure, affection, age, air bucket, bushel, calendar, carpenter, cheer, city, coast, comfort, cost, country, courage, courtesy, coward, crocodile, cruelty, damage, debt, deceit, dozen, ease, envy, error, face, faggot, fame, fault, gum, honor, joy, labor, marriage, noise, number, ocean, people, quality, river, scandal, task use, vision, and sweet*, just to mention a few.

On Literature

During the Middle English period, the overwhelming bulk of ME literature consists of religious and didactic works, and there is a heavy proportion of verse compared with prose. Verse was used for all sorts of texts because it is easier to memorize for oral retelling (Fennel, 2001). In her book, *A History of English: A Sociolinguistic Approach*, she pointed out that narrative alliterative verse was largely abandoned in favor of syllable-counting, rhymed verse while heroic poetry at that time gave way to new forms, particularly the romance, and drama appeared for the first time by the end of ME as did shorter lyric poems.

The Norton Anthology of English Literature writer, Simpson (2006) enumerated the developments of the Middle English Literature in the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries stating that by 1200, poetry and prose were being written in English (not just in French) for educated readers, and many readers were French-English bilingual. Then in the fourteenth century, there was this expansion of the merchant class and international trade, trends visible in Geoffrey Chaucer's career as a civil servant and in his portrait of the Merchant in the Canterbury Tales. Dante, Boccaccio, and Petrarch were among the new canon of literary giants who emerged in the fourteenth century. The production of mystery plays or cycles of plays that dramatized Bible stories, by city guilds, which were organizations, representing trades, and the morality play in which personified virtues and vices struggle for man's soul were all introduced in the fifteenth century.

Undeniably, the developments of medieval literature characterize these two dominant factors in the Philosophy of the Middle Ages namely the concept of Chivalry and the Church.

Published a comprehensive paper on the Historical Context for Middle English Literature, Gastle (2009) explained that during England's violent transformation in the 11th century, the church expands its reach into the Holy crusades. According to him, the Crusades provided a rich matter both as an explicit subject and as background or metaphorical material that several Middle English Romances allude to the Crusades which has influenced romance production in England. He then cited Arthurian literature such as the Alliterative Morte Arthure and Malory's subsequent *Le Morte d'Arthur* which depict King Arthur as a Crusader to further establish his Christian legitimacy to the crown. "While Boccaccio's great Italian work, the Decameron, sets several tales during the Crusades, the English poet John Gower would later draw upon the Crusades more circuitously in his tale of Constance in the *Confessio Amantis*, as would Chaucer in his version of the Constance story, *The Man of Law's Tale*," he added.

Moreover, the fellowship of chivalry/knighthood, which was considered another important institution of medieval England, has helped groom the Middle English chivalric literature. Fernando et.al. (1977) who published a book, *A Survey of English Literature*, articulated that during the middle English period, the chivalric code dictated that the ideal qualifications of a knight were courtesy, valor, generosity, loyalty, and dexterity in arms. They further detailed that the basis of the system was the military power of an arm and mounted knight whose armor and greater mobility made him more valuable than foot soldiers. Saul (2011) in his recent work analyzed the development of chivalry as a military code of behavior for the aristocracy and considered the cultural and political aspects of knighthood.

This romantic attitude would affect much of the literature of the period, especially songs and stories. Simpson (2006) noted that after the Norman Conquest, alliterative verse doubtless continued to be recited by oral poets, and at the beginning, the Gawain poet pretends that this romance is an oral poem and asks the audience to “listen” to a story, which he has “heard.” Simpson continued in his writings telling that during the late fourteenth century there was a renewed flowering of alliterative poetry, especially in the north and west of Britain, which includes *Piers Plowman* and a splendid poem known as *The Alliterative Morte Darthur* which he described Sir Gawain as the epitome of the first blooming of Arthurian chivalry where the reputation of the court rests upon his shoulders. In the Norton Anthology English literature, the following Middle English literature that survived in the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries are Sir Gawain and the Green Knight, Geoffrey Chaucer’s *The Canterbury Tales*, John Gower’s *The Lover’s Confession* and *The Tale of Philomena and Tereus*, and William England’s *The Vision of Piers Plowman*. Take a look at an example of Chaucer’s English, taken from the prologue *The Canterbury Tales* which many of the words in the lines are recognized in the Modern English period.

A knyght ther was, and that a worthy man,
That fro the tyme that he first bigan
To riden out, he loved chivalrie,
Trouthe and honour, fredom and curteisie.
Ful worthy was he in his lordes were,
And therto hadde he riden, no man ferre,
As wel in cristendom as in hethenesse,
And evere honoured for his worthynesse.

The mystics are also important in the fourteenth century. Richard Rolle, Walter Hilton and the author of *The Cloud of Unknowing* are good examples of male mystics; female mystics include Dame Julian of Norwich, who wrote *Revelations of Divine Love* in the late fourteenth century, and the author of the book of Margery Kempe from about 1430 (Fennel, 2001).

With all the towering importance of these linguistic and literary achievements, it can be claimed that Middle English period was marked by momentous changes in the English language, not only that it shows how language was shaped by the period’s political and social factors which were the result of the Norman Conquest but also it shows how English evolved from synthetic to analytic shifts that helped English language take on an identity of its own at present.

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